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Contents

Fostering Livelihood Security

1. Maternal Literacy, Child Malnutrition and Socio-Economic Security in India:
A Systematic Literature Review 1
Prof. Vandana Dwivedi, Dr. Vivek Singh & Vaishnavi Sonkar
2. Linkages Between Health, Sanitation and Water for Bringing Sustainability in an Economy 11
Aashi Gaur & Dr. Sweta Khanduri
3. Microfinance and Self-Help Groups (SHGs): A Catalyst for Rural Livelihood of Uttar Pradesh 18
Akanksha Singh, Jitendra Bahadur Pal
4. Persistence Challenges of Gender Equality and Equity in India 25
Anshu Lata & Prof. Sahab Singh
5. Fostering Livelihood Security in India: A Case Study of Education and Skill
Development in Varanasi 31
Anup Kumar Mishra
6. The Role of Gender Equity and Equality in Sustainable Economic Growth: A Health
Perspective 36
Ashpinder Kaur Grover & Dr. Monika Mehrotra
7. Rural Livelihoods Under Threat: The Impact of COVID-19 on Agriculture, Dairy,
Poultry, and Handicrafts in Eastern Uttar Pradesh 47
Balkrishna Verma & Prof. Mridula Mishra
8. Bridging the Digital Gender Divide: Technology and Women's Livelihoods 54
Ms. Bhavya Bhagat
9. Impact of SHGs on Bank Linkages in Uttarakhand 61
Deeksha Singh & Prof. (Dr) Shikha Nagalia Sharma

(vi)

10.	Exploring the Implications of the Performance of Health Indicators in the State of Uttar Pradesh: A Descriptive Study <i>Divyanshee Verma & Prof. Jyoti Pant</i>	71
11.	Are Women Secure in India? <i>Dr. Manokamana Ram & Sana Muskan</i>	80
12.	An Analytical Study of MNREGA in the Social and Economic Development of Women Workers in the Context of Uttar Pradesh <i>Dr. Udham Singh & Dr. Minhaz Husain</i>	91
13.	Skill Development in India: A Perspective on Employment <i>Dr. Ajai Kumar</i>	103
14.	Digital Literacy as a Catalyst for Socioeconomic Mobility: Addressing Urban-Rural Disparities in Indian Education Systems <i>Dr. Alok Kumar Yadav</i>	108
15.	Analysing Income Inequality by Gini and Theil Indices Methods with Focus Wage Inequality in Madhya Pradesh <i>Dr. Dolly Singh & Prof. Girish Mohan Dubey</i>	117
16.	Women Empowerment Through Vocational Education and Skill Development: A Review <i>Dr. Harish Chandra Joshi & Dr. Atul Kumar Verma</i>	130
17.	Impact of Financial Inclusion on Women Empowerment and Financial Literacy in Uttar Pradesh <i>Dr. Harnam Singh & Rajneesh Kumar Sonkar</i>	136
18.	A Study on the Rural Marketing Strategies of Hindustan Unilever Limited <i>Dr. Jeet Singh</i>	146
19.	Government Policies Practices and Solid Waste Management: A Review of Kanpur Nagar <i>Dr. Lalit Kumar Maurya, Dr. Alka Asthana & Dr. Rinku Kumar</i>	155
20.	Fiscal and Financial Stability in Uttarakhand: A Critical Study of Resource Mobilization, Public Spending, and Sustainable Economic Growth (2010-2025) <i>Dr. Namita Mishra & Komal Arya</i>	165
21.	Role of SHG'S In Strengthening the Livelihoods in Uttarakhand <i>Dr. Namita Mishra & Palakshi Mehra</i>	175
22.	Regional Disparities in the Performance of Self-Help Groups in India: An Analytical Study <i>Dr. Poonam Verma & Dr. Rajevev Yadav</i>	183
23.	Education Policy and Skill Development: Significance and Challenges <i>Dr. Praveen Kumar Jha</i>	190

(vii)

24. Industrial Skill Demand vs. Educational Supply: A Data-Driven Gap Analysis for India's Manufacturing Sector 199
Dr. Priyanka Jaiswal, Dr. Ishita Datta Ray & Urmimala Dey
25. Impact of Self-Help Groups on Socio-economic Status of Tribal Women of Uttarakhand: A Study of Kalsi And Chakrata Block 208
Dr. Radhika Bahuguna
26. Impact of Poor Sanitation on Health: A Case Study of Lucknow City 214
Dr. Rashmi Shukla
27. Empowerment of Rural Women in India: A Study of Employment and Political Representation 221
Dr. Rukmani Devi
28. Opportunities and Challenges of Gig Workers in India 231
Dr. Rupesh Kumar Singh
29. Assessing the Empowerment of Rural Women through Self-Help Groups in Valsad District, Gujarat 239
Dr. Shyamsunder Singh & Priya Yadav
30. Social Sector Expenditure as a Tool of Strengthening the Socio-Economic Security for a Resilient India 247
Dr. Sonam Gupta
31. Breaking Barriers: Addressing Poverty, Economic Inequality, and Employment in Rural Uttar Pradesh 255
Dr. Subhash Chandra & Dr. Maneesh Kumar
32. Gender Discrimination in Education in India: Evidence from Census 263
Dr. Sunil Kumar Tripathi, Dr. Rekha Gupta & Dr. Suneel Yadav
33. Role of Women Artisans in the Handloom Sector: A Study of the Banarasi Saree Industry in Varanasi 270
Dr. Vijay Kumar, Ms. Saba Parveen & Prof. Indu Upadhyay
34. MGNREGA and Rural Livelihoods: A Micro-Level Assessment of Household Income and Expenditure in Uttar Pradesh 280
Dr. Vineet Kumar Tiwari
35. Bridging the Gap: Challenges and Opportunities in Achieving Equity and Equality for Children with Special Needs (CWSN) under NEP 2020 289
Dr. Shruti Kirti Rastogi & Prof. Harishankar Singh

(viii)

36. MGNREGA as a Tool to achieve Sustainable Development Goals: Evidence from Rural India 297
Eti Goswami & Prof. Sunita Gupta
37. Impact of Education and Skill Development on Indian Economy 307
Garima Rohilla & Dr. Sweta Khanduri
38. Inter-State Comparison of Public Spending on Health and Education in India 315
Harshit Pratap Singh, Shweta Singh & Prof. Bharti Pandey
39. Does Economic Growth Reduce Inequality: A Study of GDP and Income Distribution in India 323
Kajal Kharwar & Dr. Karuna Shanker Kanaujiya
40. Skill Development and Vocational Education: A Pathway to Women's Empowerment and Sustainable Development 333
Ms. Kajal Singh, Dr. Shilpa Mishra & Dr. Radhika Chaudhary, Prof. CB Singh
41. Employment and Income Generation through the Working Market Mechanism of Rural Petty Haats in India: An Analytical Study 341
*Kunal Saxena, Anshika, Ramvir, Dr. Vikas Pradhan
Mahendra Pal, Dr. Ankita Tomar*
42. Unlocking the Potential of Industry 4.0 and HRM 4.0 for Sustainable Service Sector Growth: A Study of Job Satisfaction and Effectiveness in Uttar Pradesh and Uttarakhand 349
Mayank Chauhan, Dr. VK Singh, Mr. Rajan Singh
43. Exploring the Role of Holistic Health in Sustainable Healthcare Practices 359
Mohd Irfan Raza & Dr. Shambhu Nath Singh
44. Energy Transition in India: A Comparative Study of Uttar Pradesh and Uttarakhand 368
Mr. Jitin Soni & Prof. Uma Ratan Yadav
45. The Role of SHG Federations in Scaling UP Livelihood Interventions: A Policy Review and Ground Assessment 377
Ms. Sakshi Gupta
46. Breaking Barriers: Women's Literacy and Its Socio-Economic Impact on Bihar's Development 389
Ms. Namrata Kumari & Prof. (Dr.) Anumita Agarwal
47. Redefining Women's Economic Participation: The Transformative Role of Microfinance Institutions 396
Ms. Poonam, Dr. Alka Nayak, Dr. Shambhu Nath Singh
48. Strengthening Socio-Economic Health Equalities to Foster Livelihood Security: A Study with Special Reference to Eastern Uttar Pradesh 407
Neha Singh & Prof. Vandana Dwivedi

49.	Indian Knowledge System: Educating Minds And Enriching Skills <i>Prachi</i>	416
50.	School Sanitation and Hygiene Education: A Case Study of Prayagraj District <i>Prashant Kumar Vikram</i>	424
51.	Public Health Facilities in India: Reality and Expectations <i>Prof. Prashant Agarwal & Archana Sharma</i>	430
52.	Impact of Opportunities Created by UOCB on the Income of Farmers in Uttarakhand <i>Radha Tripathy, Dr. Kapil Lakhera & Prof. Devna Jindal Sharma</i>	443
53.	MGNREGA at the Crossroads : Development Imperative or Political Tool? <i>Raushan Kumar Singh</i>	451
54.	Changing Consumer Behavior : A Study on Natural Farming Products for a Sustainable Future <i>Shalini Singh & Dr. Parul Bhardwaj</i>	458
55.	Prospects of the Gig Economy : A Study on Education and Skill Development <i>Shweta Singh Chauhan & Prof. C.B Singh</i>	468
56.	Water Security and Health: Bridging Rural-Urban Sanitation Gaps in Uttar Pradesh <i>Mr. Arun Lal, Dr. Monika Khanna & Dr. Alok Kumar Yadav</i>	475
57.	उच्च प्राथमिक कक्षा में परम्परागत एवं ए0आई0 (कृत्रिम बुद्धिमत्ता) आधारित शिक्षण पद्धति की सारगर्भिता का तुलनात्मक अध्ययन : उत्तर प्रदेश के जनपद फतेहपुर के सन्दर्भ में <i>डॉ० भारती सिंह एवं डॉ० रिकू कुमार</i>	482
58.	शिक्षा में कौशल विकास की भूमिका का विश्लेषणात्मक अध्ययन <i>प्र० विनोद कुमार श्रीवास्तव एवं किरन पाण्डेय</i>	488
59.	भारत में महिला साक्षरता स्तर और महिला कार्य सहभागिता : एक राज्यवार विश्लेषण <i>अमित कुमार सोनकर एवं डॉ० सुरेन्द्र कुमार गुप्ता</i>	494
60.	ग्रामीण महिलाओं के सामाजिक आर्थिक विकास में स्वयं सहायता समूह की भूमिका जनपद अल्मोड़ा के विशेष संदर्भ में <i>डॉ० नमिता मिश्रा एवं ममता आर्या</i>	508
61.	भारत में क्षेत्रीय आधार पर आर्थिक असमानता : रोजगार और आय के संदर्भ में <i>डॉ० वेद प्रकाश शर्मा</i>	515

(x)

62. उत्तर प्रदेश के ग्रामीण क्षेत्रों में रोजगार सृजन और आर्थिक स्थिरता पर मनरेगा के प्रभाव का मूल्यांकन: समावेशी विकास की दिशा में एक विश्लेषण 522
निशीनाज और प्रो० डॉ० पदमा त्रिपाठी
63. स्वयं सहायता समूह आजीविका और वित्तीय समावेशन : एक अन्तर्सम्बन्ध 528
नीलम चौधरी एवं डॉ० उमारतन यादव
64. ग्रामीण भारत में महिलाओं की स्थिति 534
प्रो० किरन सिंह
65. भारत में गरीबी, बेरोजगारी और प्रवासन की चुनौतियों को कम करना 543
डॉ० वेद प्रकाश मिश्रा एवं भगवान दास
66. अल्मोडा जिले में अनुसूचित जाति के रोजगार सृजन पर स्वयं सहायता समूह की भूमिका: एक विश्लेषण 550
स्वर्णिमा गंगोला एवं डॉ० नंदन सिंह बिष्ट

A Study on the Rural Marketing Strategies of Hindustan Unilever Limited

*Dr. Jeet Singh*¹

INTRODUCTION

According to the 2011 census, there are approximately 830 million Indians living in 6,73,213 villages, making up 143 million households. The potential of the rural market is demonstrated by its magnitude. Due to the current market and economic conditions, businesses now operate in modern India, which presents difficult prospects for segmentation, targeting, and positioning. The businesses anticipate the unexplored rural markets because the urban growth rate is nearly at saturation. The rising literacy rate from 36% to 59% in rural areas, according to the 2011 census, is what draws people to this area; educated youth have access to technology and are adaptable. According to NCAER's 2010 survey, rural populations' purchasing power has also grown.

For many years, the rural market has been continuously expanding and has already surpassed the urban market in size. In India, around 70% of people reside in villages. In Indian villages, more than 800 million people reside. The new tagline of marketers is "Go rural."

Rural markets have been the focus of both Indian and international marketers, including Godrej, Colgate-Palmolive, and Hindustan Lever. Therefore, considering the prospects that village markets present to companies, it can be concluded that there is great promise available for those who can comprehend the characteristics of these rural markets and take full advantage of them.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Deepti Srivastava (2010) claims that although rural markets in India are expanding quickly, they are frequently disregarded by marketers. The rural belts are home to 53% of the market for FMCG and 59% of consumer durables. According to Md. Abbas Ali, Venkat Ram Raj Thumiki, and Naseer Khan (2012), rural marketers should create creative promotional tactics for rural markets that are appropriate for the villagers' educational and comprehension levels and can understandably convey messages. It is advised to provide long-lasting FMCG. Long-lasting features are associated with larger size and/or harder products by rural consumers. Therefore, it is advised to advertise FMCG along these lines.

According to Pawan Kumar and Neha Dangi (2013), rural India presents enormous opportunities for businesses to grow and develop, but they also face numerous obstacles when it

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comes to reaching the rural markets. With more than 800 million people living in rural India compared to around 377 million in urban India, there are a lot of unexplored opportunities in rural India, but marketers are unable to take advantage of them due to a lack of facilities especially infrastructure related matters, and the low literacy rate in rural areas makes it difficult for consumers to recognize brand differences.

According to Avinash Pareek and Dr. Satyam Pincha (2013), reaching rural audiences requires excellent communication. At one point in the late 1950s and early 1960s, radio was seen as a viable mass media tool for reaching rural populations. Cinemas and television are examples of mass media. Today, however, the situation is different. Every home in rural India had access to a television, phone, cell phone, internet, etc. The winner would ultimately be the one with the necessary financial and time resources as well as the much-needed creative ideas to reach the rural markets.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this study is to investigate India's rural marketing situation.

The objectives of this research are:

- a) To look into the marketing strategies adopted by companies in rural areas;
- b) To analyze the rural marketing strategies of Hindustan Unilever Limited.

Area of Study

The research is not related to a specific area but applies to India. This article studies the rural marketing strategies in India and considers the few research articles written on rural marketing.

TYPES OF MARKETS

- a) **Periodic Markets:** One of the key components of Indian rural marketing is the periodic market. Periodic markets are very essential to the rural economy and economic and social life of villagers, even in the face of growing urbanization and the expansion of retail outlets. Melas and periodic or weekly markets are two organizations that undertake periodic marketing.
- b) **Mobile Traders:** To satisfy the restricted demands of rural consumers, such as those for fruits, vegetables, spices, cosmetics, toiletries, clothing, utensils, etc, there is another significant organization called mobile merchants. To sell goods that rural residents frequently require, mobile traders travel from one location to another, from one home to another.
- c) **Permanent Retail Shops:** As population in villages increases, there is a rise in income level leading to increased demand for goods in rural areas. This all leads to establishment of permanent retail shops. In many circumstances, mobile traders or periodic markets are unable to cater to the needs of the villagers so retail shops emerge.

OPPORTUNITIES IN RURAL MARKETING

- a) **Broad Base of Customers:** More than 900 million people live in more than 664,000 villages. It is predicted that this population will grow annually.

- b) **Internet & Mobile Phone Usage Increased** – At the moment, there are more than 205 million Internet users in cities and more than 227 million in rural areas. In the upcoming years, this number is anticipated to rise.
- c) **Employment Opportunities Are Increasing** – Because of government initiatives over the years, rural development has resulted in financial development in rural regions. Additionally, it has raised rural residents' employment options, which has raised their income level.
- d) **Improve Literacy Rate:** The rural people are now giving importance to education. Now the children in villages are studying in good schools and colleges in villages as well as in cities. With more literacy rates, the market is also expanding.

MARKETING STRATEGIES IN RURAL AREAS

The companies apply various marketing strategies in rural areas to increase their market share. Few marketing strategies are mentioned below:

- 1) **Strategy with reference to product:** A key constituent of effective marketing in villages is product planning. Therefore, companies should work on recognizing the value of the product and its packaging, symbols and logos, and branding.
- 2) **Strategy concerning pricing:** In order to expand market share, the companies offer the most value for the money spent in rural areas and keep a reasonable price for their goods. Indian companies can achieve this by developing an aggressive cost structure. To keep product costs minimal, products should be tailor-made to the rural consumers. For example, refill packets are very helpful.
- 3) **Competitive Strategy: Companies** should focus on 5 Forces model of Michael Porter for framing the competitive strategy. (a) Supplier: Marketers must concentrate on supplies during this process. Because of this, the companies should develop and market good-quality product at reasonable prices. (b) Customer Power: Rural consumers are today well informed of their purchases than ever before due to rising literacy rates, social media, advertising, and increased awareness to urban markets. Markets must thus provide high-quality products to satisfy customer demands. (c) Potential entrants: To lessen the possibility that new competitors might show up and endure, rural marketing organizations who operate in rural markets should aim to eliminate entry obstacles by first relocating at that place and building positive connections and relations with local shopkeepers. (d) Alternative products: In rural places, counterfeiting is common, and alternatives thrive because of illiteracy, limited knowledge, and dependence on retailers in few areas. To avoid wasting the millions of rupees invested in brand development, the organization needs to have a sufficient plan in place to combat this threat. Businesses must ensure that rural clients are educated through product advertising, good packaging of products, and brand identification so they may get exactly what they desire.

- 4) **Rural Market Segmentation:** Proper segmentation of the rural market is the primary and most crucial step in the rural marketing strategy. This procedure divides a potential non-urban market into discrete sub-markets of consumers who have similar requirements and traits. The starting phase of rural marketing plan is segmenting the rural market. The target sections have to notice the company's product or brand, so the marketer uses the right marketing mix to target the identified groups of customers when segmentation is complete. **So, the business organization should involve in** focusing on target markets, focus on selected markets, and selected rural areas.
- 5) **Advertising:** Advertising by wall painting and hoarding is a very old and successful branding strategy. India's rural areas favor traditional values and a simple lifestyle. Therefore, painting the village's walls is a surefire method to get the attention of the locals.
- 6) **Mobile vans:** Audio and video make a stronger effect on anything so these media greatly influence rural consumers' perceptions of brands. Therefore, mobile vans need to be a good option for marketing in rural areas. In a single hamlet or even throughout several villages in a single day, mobile vans can also be utilized to spread the brand's image and message. Additionally, the brand's reputation in the neighborhood will be enhanced by placing product samples, bespoke flyers, and brochures in the van.
- 7) **Shop Branding:** Another excellent tactic to increase brand recognition among rural residents is shop branding. The companies must promote their brand in and around the village store or shop in order to get an instant reaction from the rural customers. Mall advertising in urban areas is equivalent to shop branding in rural marketing. Advertising a brand next to a store encourages customers to purchase the goods out of curiosity, making it a very effective rural marketing strategy.
- 8) **Kiosk Setup:** Setting up kiosks is one of the important rural marketing techniques for brands looking to engage with rural residents one-on-one. In order to draw them in, the companies must set up the kiosk in the village's well-known places, such as near schools and colleges, near the marketplace, or the bank or post office. Because of their curiosity, villagers will then be persuaded to visit the kiosk.
- 9) **Events and fairs:** The most anticipated events in the villages are Melas, or village fairs, which take place during the festivals. Nearly the whole village attends these fairs, as do the masses from the neighboring villages. Therefore, setting up a booth at these fairs is a wise strategy to attract a villager's attention to a company.

4 A's OF RURAL MARKETING

A great framework for describing the elements affecting customer behavior in rural markets is provided by the four A's of rural marketing. Businesses can target and satisfy rural customers by addressing these four factors, which will promote growth and success.

Table 1: 4 A's of Rural Marketing

<i>1. Accessibility: Covering the Gap between Rural Customers and Products</i>	<i>2. Affordability: Meeting Rural Consumers' Financial Restraints</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhance the distribution channels ; • To have effective delivery to address the rural challenges; • Improve usability for customers in rural areas. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop cost-effective distribution routes to reduce costs. • Alignment of pricing strategy with rural purchasing power; • Highlight the advantages of your goods and services to rural customers.
<i>3. Availability: Making certain that goods and services are accessible to rural customers when they need them</i>	<i>4. Awareness: Establishing Brand Recognition and Visibility</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a robust supply chain to guarantee on-time delivery. • Concentrate on inventory control to avoid stockouts and guarantee availability. • Adjust to seasonal and rural demands. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rural clientele enjoy local radio, newspapers, and other community gatherings. <p>To establish your online presence, use websites, mobile applications, and social media platforms.</p> <p>To improve public relations, cultivate connections with nearby media outlets.</p>

SWOT ANALYSIS OF RURAL MARKETING

The SWOT analysis of rural marketing is highlighted below:

Table 2: SWOT Analysis of Rural Marketing

<i>Strengths</i>	<i>Weaknesses</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Growth in Income • Growth in Literacy rate • Awareness of different brands • Large Population • The standard of living is increasing • Government support 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brand adoption is slow • Multiple languages • More personal selling • Scattered rural area leading to high distribution costs. • Less credit facilities • Poor transport facilities
<i>Opportunities</i>	<i>Threats</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Market and customers potential • Virgin markets • Creation of brand image • Promotional strategies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inequality of income • Seasonal income of villagers • Seasonal demand for the products • Prevalence of counterfeit products

ANALYSIS OF MARKETING STRATEGIES OF HINDUSTAN UNILEVER LIMITED (HUL)

In 1888, the first shipment of Sunlight soap bars reached at Kolkata's harbor, and several Lever Brothers brands quickly followed. Lifebuoy, Vim, Lux and Pears were among them. In 1931, Hindustan Vanaspati Manufacturing Company, Unilever's first Indian affiliate was established. Lever Brothers India Limited followed in 1933, and United Traders Limited followed in 1935. In the year 1956, these 3 businesses united to form Hindustan Lever Limited, which was the first of its overseas subsidiaries to offer 10 percent of its shares to the general public. In 1960s, HLL established its first Indian research center. In the 1970s, it helped the government's efforts to develop rural India by establishing industrial facilities and employment possibilities outside of large cities. In the 1990s, Pond's skincare products, Brooke Bond, and Lipton teas joined the company. And with the start of Project Shakti, a program that enables women to become micro-entrepreneurs by selling products in their communities, HLL's dedication to bolstering livelihoods throughout rural India intensified as the new millennium drew near. In 2007, HLL became Hindustan Unilever Limited. Additionally, Horlicks and Boost, consumer health brands from GlaxoSmithKline, joined HUL's flourishing portfolio in 2020.

Strategies adopted by HUL

The various strategies adopted by HUL to increase its market share are highlighted below:

- 1) Reasonably priced Products: HUL leverages value engineering to produce reasonably priced goods that satisfy rural consumers' price sensitivity.
- 2) Reduced Pack Dimensions: To accommodate rural consumers' lower income levels, they provide their products in smaller, more economical pack sizes, for example packs of Rs. 5 or Rs. 10
- 3) Direct Distribution Networks: To increase access to their products in far-flung locations, HUL has set up direct distribution networks with rural vendors and retailers.
- 4) Project Shakti: The idea of educating indigenous women to work as door-to-door sales representatives for Unilever products in rural areas was first introduced by HUL. Through door-to-door sales conducted in over 100,000 communities in collaboration with self-help organizations of women entrepreneurs in rural areas, this initiative empowers women and expands access to HUL products.
- 5) Tailored Products and Packaging: To meet the unique requirements and tastes of rural customers, HUL also employs tailored products, packaging, and marketing.
- 6) Awareness Program "Khusiyon Ki Doli": HUL started an initiative which aims to educate rural communities about their products and their uses.
- 7) Reestablishing Contact with Customers: In order to better understand the needs and preferences of its rural customers, HUL has taken steps to reestablish contact with them through feedback, store visits, and conversations.
- 8) Rural Marketing Initiatives: HUL's efforts, such as the "Streamline system," have improved the availability of HUL brands and SKUs in village stores and extended their direct reach in rural markets.

- 9) Assist managers in embracing a rural perspective: A program that mandates managers live in a hamlet for a month during their first year is the foundation of HUL's success in rural India. They gain a firsthand look at the demands and goals of rural consumers by seeing how they live. They learn things from their own experience that they would never learn by reading papers or going to traditional markets.

With more than 800 million internet users, India has the world's greatest per-user mobile data consumption. Teams at HUL are spearheading a future-fit agenda aimed at redefining how the company uses technology to function, interact with customers, and harness the power of data as a result of the market's increasing digitization.

Projects of HUL

- 1) **Project Bharat**, the first and biggest rural home-to-home initiative ever prepared by a firm, was started in 1998 by HUL's personal products division. By the end of 1999, 13 million rural families were included in the project. Throughout the operation, HUL used vans to travel to communities all over the nation and hand out sample packs that included inexpensive packs of skin cream, toothpaste, talcum powder, and shampoo, each costing Rs 15. This was done in order to raise awareness of the company's product categories and their affordability.
- 2) HUL has launched **Project Streamline**, a major endeavor with long-term advantages, to increase its rural reach with the assistance of rural sub-stockists. Six thousand sub-stockists were hired. Consequently, the distribution network reached over 250 million people by directly covering 50,000 villages. This increased the company's direct reach to 37 percent of the rural population in the nation and provided it with the necessary competitive edge. In order to drive distribution in villages using non-traditional modes of transportation like tractors, bullock carts, etc., a rural distributor will have about 20 stockists working for him.
- 3) **Project Shakti** was the creative, socially conscious project that HUL came up with. It significantly alters the paradigm for rural communication and distribution, compellingly reaching a sizable portion of rural Indians. Hindustan Lever, rural women, and customers all benefit from the cooperation that Project Shakti establishes. Project Shakti gives women from self-help groups the opportunity to start their own micro-businesses and distribute Hindustan Lever directly to their homes. Each of the selected villages had a Shakti entrepreneur who was a member of a Self Help Group (SHG). As Shakti brand ambassadors, or Shakti Ammas, they obtained loans from their local Self-Help Groups and used the funds to buy HUL goods to sell in their communities. Thus, Project Shakti is a very interactive sales and engagement strategy that takes use of a special chance to explain, illustrate, and offer the advantages of the HUL brand.

Challenges of HUL's FMCG products in Rural Market

1. The growing rivalry amongst many Fast Moving Consumer Goods businesses.
2. Retail FDI, which permits global brands.
3. Local and unbranded products pose a threat.

4. The presence of competing, powerful Fast Moving Consumer Goods brands limits market share.
5. International and major domestic competitors pose a serious threat to HUL products.

Opportunities for HUL in Rural Market

1. Expand reach in metropolitan locations and reach out to rural markets.
2. Acquisitions and mergers to bolster the brand in rural areas.
3. People's growing purchasing power, which raises demand for HUL goods.
4. The potential for change is increasingly apparent as the IT culture and electronic ethos spread throughout rural India.

SUGGESTIONS

In rural areas, electronic media advertisements are preferred over other forms of communication. If HUL can convince rural residents that they are valued as consumers, they stand to gain the most. In rural marketing, regional languages play a crucial role. Rural consumers are becoming more and more brand-aware, and as a result, prices and offers should be tailored to their preferences. In the rural market, the spouse makes the decisions after the individual, thus attention must be paid to them through various channels or initiatives, such as counseling, etc.

CONCLUSION

Long-term success, according to HUL's objective, necessitates a complete dedication to extraordinary performance and productivity standards as well as a readiness to accept new ideas and never stop learning. Thus, creativity is ingrained in HUL's culture. As a result, numerous product improvements were created, and the company also innovated in distribution, which sparked the birth of other projects, chief among them being Project Shakthi, a modified microcredit model. In addition to significantly contributing to the economic growth of rural India, this project, Shakthi, also improved the lives of rural women and catalyzed women's empowerment.

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